

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА КЛИНИК
ТИББИЁТ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ
ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF THE SMALL INTESTINAL AND LYMPHOID STRUCTURES OF WHITE OUTBRED RATS**Oripova N.A.**

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Resume. *The epithelium of the intestinal mucosa is composed of four main types of cells - absorptive enterocytes, goblet cells, Paneth cells and enteroendocrine cells, which are constantly renewed. The study of the structure, morphology and morphometry of the small intestine of the white-bred rat makes a significant contribution to the field of morphology. This article presents data on the morphometric characteristics of the components of the small intestine of the white-bred rat.*

Keywords: *white outbred rat, small intestine, morphology, morphometry, lymphoid structures, intestinal villi.*

ОҚ ЗОТСИЗ КАЛАМУШЛАР ИНГИЧКА ИЧАГИ ВА ЛИМФОИД ТУЗИЛМАЛАРИНИНГ МОРФОМЕТРИК КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИ**Орипова Н.А.**

Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти, Бухоро ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. *Ичак шиллиқ қаватининг эпителийси тўрт асосий турдаги хужайралардан ташкил топган – абсорбцияловчи энтероцитлар, жомсимон хужайралар, Панет хужайралари ва энтероэндокрин хужайралар, улар узлуксиз янгиланади. Оқ зотсиз каламушлар ингичка ичаги структур тузилиши, морфологияси ва морфометриясини ўрганиш морфология соҳасига катта ҳисса қўшади. Ушбу мақолада оқ зотсиз каламушларнинг ингичка ичаги таркибий қисмларининг морфометрик хусусиятлари ҳақида маълумотлар келтирилган.*

Калит сўзлар: *оқ зотсиз каламушлар, ингичка ичак, морфология, морфометрия, лимфоид тузилмалар, ичак ворсинкалари.*

МОРФОМЕТРИЧЕСКИЕ ПАРАМЕТРЫ И ЛИМФОИДНЫЕ СТРУКТУРЫ ТОНКОГО КИШЕЧНИКА БЕЛЫХ БЕСПОРОДНЫХ КРЫС**Орипова Н.А.**

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Резюме. *Эпителий слизистой оболочки кишечника состоит из четырёх основных типов клеток – всасывающих энтероцитов, бокаловидных клеток, клеток Панета и энтероэндокринных клеток, которые постоянно обновляются. Изучение структуры, морфологии и морфометрии тонкого кишечника белых крыс вносит значительный вклад в область морфологии. В данной статье представлены данные о морфометрической характеристике компонентов тонкого кишечника белых крыс.*

Ключевые слова: *белая беспородная крыса, тонкий кишечник, морфология, морфометрия, лимфоидные структуры, кишечные ворсинки.*

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Relevance The gastrointestinal tract is constantly exposed to various physical and chemical factors. The interaction of bacteria with epithelial cells in the intestine is largely dependent on mucus, which is mainly composed of highly glycosylated mucin-2, secreted by the goblet cells of the mucosal epithelium. Goblet cells are located along the entire length of the small and large intestine and are responsible for the development and maintenance of the protective layer of mucus through the synthesis and secretion of high-molecular glycoproteins known as mucins [1, 2]. Today, the main task of biological experiments is to study the fundamental mechanisms of the body's adaptation to the effects of physical and chemical factors at the cellular, tissue, and organ levels. In this case, the gastrointestinal tract is the first to respond to exogenous influences of various genesis [6,7].

Intestinal epithelial cells, along with food, are in constant contact with many foreign antigens that enter biological barriers, the main function of which is to maintain the body's homeostasis. The epithelial integrity necessary for this is ensured by intensive processes of cell regeneration. Among the cells of the intestinal

epithelium, a separate group of cells is distinguished - goblet cells (GC), which belong to the so-called mucus-secreting glands. Their name corresponds to the shape of the cells determined during histological studies. The apex of the GC has an expanded, secretory, C-shaped rim of the cytoplasm, called theca, and a narrow base descending to the basal lamina. They produce mucin to lubricate the intestinal contents and protect the epithelium [3, 8]. Mucin type II, which is secreted by the intestinal mucosa and colon, is abundant in the mucosa of the small and large intestine (MUC2, mucin-2). Intestinal epithelial cells also express transmembrane mucins (MUC 1, MUC 3, MUC 4, MUC 12, MUC 13, and MUC 17), which adhere to the apical surface and, together with glycolipids, form a glycocalyx. Mast cells are found in the middle zone of the crypts and are the source of most of the cell types in the intestinal epithelium. The nucleus of the mast cell is located at the base of the long axis and has an apical zone with numerous membrane-bound mucin granules. Their apical surface bears several short microvilli, and in the supranuclear region is the Golgi apparatus with a basally localized rough endoplasmic reticulum. Their secretion plays an important role in chemical and mechanical protection and lubrication of the intestinal wall, as well as in its immune defense, since together with the above, IgA class antibodies are secreted. The GH absorbs IgA, which is initially secreted by B lymphocytes present in the lamina propria, by endocytosis, at its base and sides, and this provides the main source of protection against microbial organisms in the intestinal lumen [4, 9]. The GH appears as a foreign body located intermittently between the columnar cells of the intestinal epithelium. Their number increases in the direction of the distal part of the small intestine. The contribution of JH among epithelial cells increases caudally from the duodenum (4%) to the distal colon (16%), as does the increase in the number of microbial organisms present from the proximal region of the intestine to the colon [10].

The aim of the study was to study the morphometric characteristics of the small intestinal and lymphoid structures of 5-month-old white outbred rats.

Research materials and methods For experimental studies, 5-month-old white outbred male rats weighing 190-230 g were selected. All laboratory animals were kept in the same vivarium environment and fed the same food. The feeding, care, grouping of laboratory animals, and work with them were carried out in accordance with the rules of biological safety and ethical principles.

The study of the macromorphology of the small intestine, the micromorphology of the mucous membrane and the submucosal base was carried out in 180 5-month-old male white rats in normal vivarium conditions. The animals were killed by decapitation at an appropriate time in the morning, on an empty small intestine, under ether anesthesia. The main objects of the study were histological preparations prepared from the organs of white male rats.

The preparation of histological preparations consisted of 4 stages and was carried out using traditional methods. A microtome was used to prepare the preparations, and the prepared sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin. For this, the sections were immersed in hematoxylin solution for 3-5 minutes, then washed with water. After the nuclei were stained purple (observed under a microscope), they were stained in eosin solution for 0.5-1.5 minutes, washed in distilled water and dehydrated using increasing concentrations of alcohol (from 70° to 100°). To remove alcohol from the section and fix it, they were placed in three successive portions of O-xylene and embedded in Canada balsam. The sections were examined morphometrically, and the size of the small intestine walls was measured using an ocular micrometer.

Research results. In 5-month-old rats, the thickness of the wall of the initial part of the mesentery of the small intestine ranges from 724.5 to 959.2 μm . The greatest thickness is observed in the lateral walls (mean -823.2 ± 3.0) compared to the mesenteric walls (mean -733.4 ± 2.5 μm) and the walls of the opposite part of the mesentery (mean -654.7 ± 2.1 μm).

The thickness of the lateral walls of the mucous membrane in the initial part of the mesentery of the small intestine (mean -713.7 ± 2.2 μm) is 1.14 times greater than the thickness of the mesenteric mucosa (mean -626.4 ± 3.7 μm) and the walls of the opposite part of the mesentery (mean -548.2 ± 2.6 μm).

Villi and crypts are structural elements of the mucosa. The surface of the mucous membrane is covered with villi.

In the walls of the mesenteric section of the small intestine of 5-month-old rats, the villi of the initial part vary in height: on the lateral walls they are the longest (average 643.5 ± 3.8 μm) and finger-shaped (Fig. 1), on the mesenteric wall (average -566.2 ± 2.5 μm) and on the mesenteric wall (average -495.1 ± 2.8 μm) they have a leaf-shaped or triangular shape with a wide base.

The total area of the small intestine group lymphoid nodes along its length varied from 90.3 mm^2 to 131.2 mm^2 , with an average of -111.0 ± 0.4 mm^2 . The area occupied by the GLU averages 2.3% of the total area of the small intestine.

Figure 1. The small intestine wall of a 5-month-old rat in the control group. Hematoxylin-eosin staining. Magnification 10 x 20. 1. High growth of the mucosal villi (single-layer prismatic epithelium). Extrusion of the epithelium into the intestinal cavity. Serous inflammatory infiltrate. 2. Hyperplasia of the glands located in the lamina propria: hyperchromatic staining of the nucleus, shrinkage of the cytoplasm. 3. Submucosal layer: Hypertrophy of sparse fibrous connective tissue, vascular congestion, lymphocyte infiltrate. 4. In the muscular layer: hypertrophy of muscle fibers, edema in the intermuscular space.

The cellular composition of the lymphoid node consists of 57.2% small lymphocytes, 20.9% medium lymphocytes, and 15.7% large lymphocytes.

Crypts are tubular recesses located in the epithelium of the intestinal mucosa, in the lamina propria of the mucosa. The depth of the crypts of the initial part of the mesentery of the small intestine ranges from 40.2 to 89.6 μm , with deeper crypts located on the lateral walls (mean $-71.3 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{m}$) relative to the walls of the mesentery (mean $-60.1 \pm 47.3 \mu\text{m}$) and the opposite part of the mesentery (mean $-54.8 \pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$).

The thickness of the submucosal layer in the initial part of the mesentery of the small intestine ranges from 19.1 to 58.3 μm . This layer is thicker in the opposite part of the mesentery (mean $-30.2 \pm 2.4 \mu\text{m}$) and in the mesentery wall (mean $-30.6 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{m}$) than in the lateral walls (mean $-30.3 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{m}$).

The thickness of the muscularis serosa varies along the circumference of the small intestine wall and ranges from 72.1 μm to 108.2 μm . There is a slight difference in the thickness of the walls of the manubrium (mean $-75.7 \pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$) and the contralateral part of the manubrium (mean $-75.9 \pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$) compared with the lateral (mean $-76.3 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{m}$).

The total area of GLU of the small intestine along its entire length ranged from 142.3 mm^2 to 181.1 mm^2 , with an average of $164.0 \pm 0.35 \text{mm}^2$. The area occupied by GLU averaged 2.7% of the total area of the small intestine.

In 5-month-old rats, the wall thickness of the mesenteric section of the small intestine varied from 545.1 μm to 793.2 μm . The greatest thickness was observed in the lateral walls (average $-746.3 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{m}$) compared to the mesenteric (average $-634.0 \pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$) and the mesenteric (average $-618.3 \pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$) walls.

The thickness of the lateral walls of the middle part of the mesentery of the small intestine (average $-622.4 \pm 3.3 \mu\text{m}$) is 1.3 times greater than the thickness of the mesentery mucosa (average $-625.1 \pm 2.2 \mu\text{m}$) and the mucosa of the opposite part of the mesentery (average $-532.2 \pm 2.3 \mu\text{m}$).

The mucosa contains villi that protrude into the intestinal cavity.

The height and shape of the villi around the wall of the mesentery of the small intestine are not the same. The lateral walls are on average the longest $-603.6 \pm 2.1 \mu\text{m}$ and have a finger-like shape, on average $-541.7 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{m}$ on the mesentery wall and on average $-494.4 \pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ on the wall of the opposite part of the mesentery, they are leaf-shaped or triangular with a wide base.

Crypts - depressions, the mouths of which open into the intestinal cavity between the villi. The depth of the crypts in the middle part of the mesentery of the small intestine ranges from 46.8 to 71.4 μm , with deeper crypts located on the lateral walls (mean $-64.8 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{m}$) relative to the mesentery (mean $-56.2 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{m}$) and the walls of the opposite part of the mesentery (mean $-52.5 \pm 1.4 \mu\text{m}$).

Figure 2. The small intestine wall of a 5-month-old rat in the control group. Hematoxylin-eosin staining. Ok. 10 x ob. 20. 1. Hyperplasia of the glands located in the lamina propria: hyperchromatic staining of the nucleus, shrinkage of the cytoplasm. 2. In the lamina propria of the mucosa: hypertrophy of sparse fibrous unformed connective tissue, edema and inflammatory infiltrate. 3. Submucosa: hypertrophy of sparse fibrous connective tissue, vascular congestion, lymphocyte infiltrate.

The thickness of the submucosal layer in the middle part of the mesentery of the small intestine in 5-month-old rats ranges from 19.4 to 45.8 μm . This layer is more pronounced on the opposite part of the mesentery (mean $-27.1 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{m}$) and the edges of the mesentery (mean $-28.7 \pm 1.6 \mu\text{m}$) than on the lateral (mean $-30.6 \pm 1.5 \mu\text{m}$) walls.

The thickness of the musculoserosa of the middle part of the small intestine mesentery in 5-month-old rats varies along the circumference (Fig. 2). It is greater in the lateral (mean $-67.6 \pm 1.4 \mu\text{m}$) and contralateral (mean $-69.7 \pm 1.2 \mu\text{m}$) walls than in the mesenteric (mean $-72.0 \pm 1.5 \mu\text{m}$) walls.

The thickness of the wall of the terminal part of the small intestine mesentery in 5-month-old rats ranges from 554.0 μm to 795.1 μm . The greatest thickness is observed in the lateral walls (mean $-683.7 \pm 3.1 \mu\text{m}$) compared to the mesenteric (mean $-614.3 \pm 3.2 \mu\text{m}$) and contralateral (mean $-499.0 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{m}$) walls.

The thickness of the mucosa in the final part of the mesentery of the small intestine on the side walls (average $-635.2 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{m}$) is 1.0 times greater than the thickness of the mesentery mucosa (average $-520.7 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{m}$) and the mucosa of the opposite part of the mesentery (average $-482.3 \pm 2.6 \mu\text{m}$).

The mucous membrane is filled with villi. The villi of the side walls are the longest (average $-507.3 \pm 2.4 \mu\text{m}$) and have a finger-like shape. The villi of the mesentery (average $-523.5 \pm 3.0 \mu\text{m}$) and the edge of the opposite part of the mesentery (average $-476.2 \pm 2.6 \mu\text{m}$) are triangular in shape, with a wide base.

Crypts are tubular recesses in the epithelium of the intestinal mucosa located in the special plate of the intestinal mucosa. The depth of the crypts in the terminal part of the small intestine mesentery ranges from 33.8 to 69.3 μm , with deeper crypts located on the lateral walls (average $-59.4 \pm 1.2 \mu\text{m}$) relative to the mesentery (average $-52.7 \pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$) and the wall opposite the mesentery (average $-47.6 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{m}$).

The thickness of the submucosal layer in the middle part of the small intestine mesentery ranges from 15.6 to 29.2 μm . This layer is well developed in the mesentery opposite the mesentery (average $-23.1 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{m}$) and at the edge of the mesentery (average $-20.6 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$) relative to the lateral walls (average $-19.8 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$).

The muscular layer of the mesentery consists of an inner circular and an outer longitudinal layer. The thickness of the musculoserosous membrane of the final part of the mesentery of the small intestine varies along the circumference. It is most pronounced in the lateral walls (average $-61.7 \pm 1.5 \mu\text{m}$) and the opposite part of the mesentery (average $-60.6 \pm 1.4 \mu\text{m}$) and in the mesentery walls ($60.1 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{m}$).

Conclusion The epithelium of the intestinal mucosa is composed of four main types of cells - absorptive enterocytes, goblet cells, Paneth cells and enteroendocrine cells, which are constantly renewed. The study of the structure, morphology and morphometry of the small intestine of the white-bred rat makes a significant contribution to the field of morphology.

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